

Bama's Karukku Portrayed an Achievement to be an Identity of Vitality, Virtuous Venture of Voice and a Cheerful Cleverness of Confidence

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Abstract

Karukku is both fiction and autobiography in a duel of ways. In Bama's life Karukku is to find out her own identity. In her life she had lost everything. She felt, she was a stranger to society. In her village she was a stranger to society. In her village she was spent more happy life. Karukku explains recollection of her past life in the village. Karukku explains to the crisis of the Dalit, of the untouchable, how class treat in the rural setting serves to calm voice.

Bama shows in this novel about how the difficult of the Dalit is one of the bad outrages. Dalits have been told again and again of their loss of dignity, they have come to believe they are disrespect they have reached a stage where they themselves, willingly, hold on to themselves apart. The result of all this is that there is no way for Dalits to realize freedom or retrieval. Had Bama naturally written a work that only useful to herself in the structure of her own story, she might not have been able to expanse as numerous people? Bama desires to deliver voice to as class structure in a nation that has openly said that there is no class structure. In this novel shows Bama's personal critical point and separated in her life which moves to make intention of her life which moves to make intention of her life as woman, Christian, Dalit.

Keywords: Untouchable, Outrage, Dignity, Dalit.

Meaning of Karukku is Palmyra leaves which with their jagged sharpness on both sides, are like double-barreled weapon. By a delicious pun, the Tamil word Karukku, encase the word seed, also means span-new. In her prelude, Bama to make attention to the emblem and refers to the words in Hebrews (New Testament). In Karukku, Bama concentrates the unsecured condition of Dalit people how they are loss of destiny due to their poor economic background. The abide country less farming laborers who are economically helpless.

She gives importance to other main issue such as unreliability, intolerance in the modern church, Christianity. She harmfully to notice that their wealthy civilization is despoiled and they are left

with no civilization. She shows in this novel about the Dalit Christians have been oppression. So the Dalit people have oppressed in every caste such as Hindu, Christian, and Muslim. They live separately because normal people not treat Dalit people as their equals.

Bama concentrates the inequalities that history and heritage frequent upon Dalit women. On the one hand there is the black perspective of liberation and, on the other clear perspective of fate. They, however, purpose for cultural sociable, profitable and political reform and they do not look back. They continue to be oppressive people, who are undeniable. The Dalit woman who wants to need job in an urban is making a symbolic message. She gets more suffering for job. She is travel more for job that gets shameless in their society. They did not give equal rights to them. They do only small jobs such as sweeps, making clean into drains and the toilets. From her birth to death, she has to follow all the rules of the society and also the men folk at home. In many Dalit families have no freedom for anything. Similarly like caged birds. Without feathers birds cannot fly. Likewise Dalit families have not got their rights.

Below these bad conditions, the Dalit woman would discover a social equality as well as economic free equality. They were faced three types of bad conditions: Dalit people have affected with caste and other people treated them to untouchability and inequality. These things affected both male and female oppressed by the form of the Hindu religious system. Get more sufferings from their society. They only get pain, sad, domination and inequality.

Bama gives more importance for education. Education gives us knowledge and it helps to people how to behavior in outside. She says Education is self-serving Government. Education helps to Dalit people for decrease poverty. Education gives values of Dalit people especially for their rights. Through the education they break all the rules and conditions in their society. Without education Dalits gets only upper caste domination and untouchability. Education improves their social status, economic and political power. No one understands their values. But Bama shows through this novel everyone needs self-discipline, self-esteem, self-reliance, self-concept and self-perception especially for Dalits.

No one understands value of human life, especially Dalits life. Upper caste people showered no sympathy on Dalits when they bad condition. Dalit people not only suffered caste problem. They suffered more in different ways especially black women, injustice and that is not free from racism. Dalit have more miseries in their life. Bama focused all the things and explains through this novel. Bama's life arranges in different order, as with most autobiographies.

It shows different themes, especially work, games, recreation and etc. Bama gives in this novel about more aspects of Christianity, equality, justice and all kind of people need love. She explains her own life and experience share with reader. It is actively engaging in alienated the sufferings of bad conditions. Finally, Bama makes the only chance possible for developing awareness for Dalit people. Her own life and experience is a major part of Dalits. Bama's life is a model of other people.

She leaves her religious order and moved to her native place, she feels her life is insecure, but she does not feel complicated. She mainly focused in this novel of identity. She suffered identity, but she change which means at the end that get identity in their society. She uses a Dalit style of writing, especially she follow separate rules of grammar and spelling. But the reader can understand easily of her writing. She shares everything directly.

Reader read this novel and take resolution of how to behaviour and how to treat others equally. Karukku explains simply of life and the values of life. Every people need identity in this society.

But some people not realize that. Karukku tells these are all the things to the people. Bama's Karukku is good example of others. This work speaks wants to live hopefully and shows what the matter of life is. She shows in this novel reality of life.

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